

On the Existence of Solutions of Multi-Term Fractional Order Volterra Integro-Differential Equations

D. Umar ^{1*}, S. L. Bichi ²

1. Department of Mathematics, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Nigeria.
 2. Department of Mathematical Sciences, Bayero University Kano, Nigeria.
- * Corresponding author: dah4bab@mau.edu.ng*, slawanbh@gmail.com

Article Info

Received: 21 January 2024 Revised: 11 August 2024
Accepted: 10 November 2024 Available online: 15 December 2024

Abstract

In this paper, the problem of multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equations is considered. The multi-term fractional order derivative part of the multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equations is converted to its equivalent integral equation and Schauder's fixed point theorem is applied to establish the existence of solutions for the multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equations under some mild conditions. Furthermore, examples were given to test the applicability of the proposed theorem.

Keywords: Existence of Solution, Fractional Integro-Differential Equation, Schauder's Fixed Point Theorem, Volterra Integro-Differential Equation.

MSC2010: 26A33, 34A08, 45D05, 47H10.

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematical analysis which deals with the investigation and applications of integral and derivatives of arbitrary order. Therefore, it is the generalization of classical calculus, involving derivatives and integrals of real or complex order [1]. Many physical events are more desirably explained by fractional derivatives because it considers the evolution of system into account. However, it is sometimes difficult to find exact solutions for some of these equations. Hence, the need for a numerical approach. In the past few decades, a number of numerical approaches for approximation of solutions to this class of equations have found applications in various field of sciences, engineering and social sciences such as chaotic systems [2], Fluid Mechanics [3], Viscoelasticity [4], Optimal Control problems [5], Biology [6], Physics [7], Bioengineering [8], Finance [9], Social Sciences [10], Economics [11], Optics [12], Chemical Reactions [13] and Rheology [14]. Furthermore, numerous scholars have proposed and studied the existence and uniqueness of solutions of these equations such as [15] and [16] studied the existence of solution of multi-term fractional order Fredholm integro-differential equation and Uniqueness and convergence of solution of multi-term fractional order Fredholm Integro-differential equation, respectively. While [17] studied the uniqueness of solution of multi-term fractional order Volterra Integro-differential equation

with convergence analysis, [18] proved the existence results for fractional integro-differential equations with nonlocal condition via resolvent operators. Also, the existence of solutions of various types of fractional differential equations and fractional integro-differential equations of boundary value problems and initial value problems were explored recently by [18–36], and so many more. A special class of these equations are the Volterra type, it has been used to describe heat transfer issues, nano hydrodynamics, mass diffusion processes, neutron diffusion, biological species coexisting together with diminishing and increasing rate of growth, and electromagnetic theory [38]

In this study, we considered the multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equation of the form

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) D^{\gamma_i} y(x) + g(x) + \int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \quad (1.1)$$

subject to the initial condition

$$\begin{aligned} y^{(k)}(0) &= d_k, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1, \\ m-1 &< \alpha \leq m, \quad 0 < \gamma_0 < \gamma_1 < \dots < \gamma_i < \alpha, \quad m, n \in \mathbb{N}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

where D is the differential operator defined in Caputo sense, $y : Q = [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function which needs to be determined, $u_i, g : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given continuous functions, $K : Q \times Q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the kernel of integration which is also continuous, $G : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Lipschitz function.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. (Compact Map [39]). Let X and Y be Banach spaces and let $\Omega \subseteq X$. A map $F : \Omega \rightarrow Y$ is said to be compact if it is continuous and $F(\Omega)$ is relatively compact (i.e, for every $(x_n)_n \subseteq \Omega$, there exists a subsequence $(x_{n_j})_j$ of $(x_n)_n$ such that $F(x_{n_j})_j$ is convergent).

Definition 2.2. (Uniformly Bounded [1]). A set M is called uniformly bounded if there exists a constant $K > 0$ such that $\|m\|_\infty \leq K$ for every $m \in M$.

Definition 2.3. (Equicontinuous [1]). A set M is called equicontinuous if, for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists some $\delta > 0$ such that, for all $m \in M$ and all $x_1, x_2 \in [a, b]$ with $|x_1 - x_2| < \delta$, we have $|m(x_1) - m(x_2)| < \epsilon$.

Theorem 1. (Arzelà-Ascoli [1]). Let M be a subset of $C[a, b]$ equipped with the norm $(\|\cdot\|_\infty)$. Then M is relatively compact in $C[a, b]$ if and only if, M is equicontinuous and uniformly bounded.

Theorem 2. (Schauder's Fixed Point Theorem [39]). Let C be a nonempty, closed, bounded and convex subset of a Banach space X and let $T : C \rightarrow C$ be compact. Then T has a fixed point.

Proposition 2.4. (Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral [1]). Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order α of a function y is defined as

$$I^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} y(s) ds, \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+, \quad (2.1)$$

where \mathbb{R}^+ is the set of positive real numbers.

Proposition 2.5. (Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative [1]). Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of order α of a function y is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{RL}D^\alpha y(x) &= D^m I^{m-\alpha} y(x), \quad m-1 < \alpha \leq m, \quad m \in \mathbb{N} \\ &= \frac{d^m}{dt^m} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{m-\alpha-1} y(s) ds \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

Proposition 2.6. (*Caputo Fractional Derivative [1]*). The fractional derivative of $y(x)$ in the Caputo sense is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^C D^\alpha y(x) &= I^{m-\alpha} D^m y(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{m-\alpha-1} \frac{d^m y(s)}{ds^m} ds, \quad m-1 < \alpha \leq m. \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

with the following properties

- (i) $I^\alpha D^\alpha y(x) = y(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(0)}{k!} x^k$, $m-1 < \alpha \leq m$,
- (ii) $I^\alpha D^\gamma y(x) = I^{\alpha-\gamma} y(x)$, $0 < \gamma < \alpha$, and $m-1 < \alpha \leq m, m \in \mathbb{N}$,
- (iii) $I^\alpha y(x) = \frac{x^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}$, where $y(x) = 1$, $x \in [0, 1]$

3 Preliminary results

Throughout this work, we denote by

i $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ the sup norm on $C(Q, \mathbb{R})$, i.e for $u \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$, $\|u\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in Q} |u(x)|$.

ii $\Lambda := \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\|u_i\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha-\gamma_i+1)}$.

Lemma 1. Let $y : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous functions. Then, a function y is a solution to the fractional integro-differential equation (1.1) – (1.2) if and only if,

$$y(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} x^k + \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) I^{\alpha-\gamma_i} y(s) + I^\alpha g(s) + I^\alpha \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right). \quad (3.1)$$

Proof. Applying (2.1) on (1.1) and using property (i), (ii) and (iii) we have,

$$\begin{aligned} I^\alpha (D^\alpha y(x)) &= I^\alpha \left(\sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) D^{\gamma_i} y(x) \right) + I^\alpha (g(x)) + I^\alpha \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) I^\alpha (D^{\gamma_i} y(x)) + I^\alpha (g(x)) + I^\alpha \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{y^{(k)}(0)}{k!} x^k + \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) I^{\alpha-\gamma_i} y(s) + I^\alpha g(s) + \\ &\quad I^\alpha \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} x^k + \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) I^{\alpha-\gamma_i} y(s) + I^\alpha g(s) + I^\alpha \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, y solves (1.1) – (1.2) if and only if, y solves (3.1) □

Lemma 2. Let X and Y be normed linear spaces and let $f : A \rightarrow Y$ be a Lipschitz map, $A \subseteq X$. Then f sends bounded sets to bounded sets.

Proof. For any set $E \subseteq A$, if there exists $M > 0 : \|x\|_X \leq M$ for all $x \in E$, then we show that there exists $\tilde{M} > 0 : \|f(x)\|_Y \leq \tilde{M}$ for all $x \in E$. Since f is Lipschitz, that is, there exists $L > 0$ such that

$$\|f(x) - f(y)\|_Y \leq L \|x - y\|_X \text{ for all } x, y \in A.$$

Let x_0 be a fixed element of A . Then, if there exists $M > 0 : \|x\|_X \leq M$ for all $x \in E$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} \|f(x)\|_Y &= \|f(x) - f(x_0) + f(x_0)\|_Y \\ &\leq \|f(x) - f(x_0)\|_Y + \|f(x_0)\|_Y \\ &\leq L \|x - x_0\|_X + \|f(x_0)\|_Y \\ &\leq L (\|x\|_X + \|x_0\|_X) + \|f(x_0)\|_Y \\ &\leq L (M + \|x_0\|_X) + \|f(x_0)\|_Y. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\|f(x)\|_Y \leq \tilde{M}$ for all $x \in E$, where $\tilde{M} = L (M + \|x_0\|_X) + \|f(x_0)\|_Y$. Hence, $f(E)$ is bounded. Thus, f sends bounded sets to bounded sets \square

Lemma 3. For any $0 \leq a < b$,

$$b^\alpha - a^\alpha \leq (b - a)^\alpha, \alpha \in (0, 1).$$

Proof. Define $f : [0, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$f(t) = (b - t)^\alpha - b^\alpha + t^\alpha, t \in [0, b), \tag{3.2}$$

Then from equation (3.2)

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &= (b - t)^\alpha - b^\alpha + t^\alpha \\ &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Case I. Suppose $\alpha = 0$, then for any $0 \leq a < b$ we have from equation (3.2)

$$\begin{aligned} f(a) &= 1 \\ &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Case II (a). Suppose $\alpha > 0$, and $f(t)$ is increasing, then we have from equation (3.2)

$$f'(t) = -\alpha \left((b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \right) \geq 0.$$

Thus,

$$(b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \leq 0.$$

Hence,

$$t \geq \frac{b}{2}.$$

(b) Suppose $\alpha > 0$, and $f(t)$ is decreasing, then we have from equation (3.2)

$$f'(t) = -\alpha \left((b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \right) \leq 0.$$

Thus,

$$(b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \geq 0.$$

Hence,

$$t \leq \frac{b}{2}.$$

So, f is decreasing on $[0, \frac{b}{2}]$ and increasing on $[\frac{b}{2}, b)$. Hence, $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = f(0) = 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow b^-} f(t) = f(b) = 0$, i.e., $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = f(0)$ or $f(b)$. Thus, $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = 0$. Therefore, for any $0 \leq a < b$, $f(a) \geq \inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = 0$, i.e.,

$$(b - a)^\alpha - b^\alpha + a^\alpha \geq 0,$$

that is,

$$b^\alpha - a^\alpha \leq (b - a)^\alpha.$$

Case III (a). Suppose $\alpha < 0$, and $f(t)$ is increasing, then we have from equation (3.2)

$$f'(t) = -\alpha \left((b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \right) \geq 0.$$

Thus,

$$(b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \geq 0.$$

Hence,

$$t \leq \frac{b}{2}.$$

(b) Suppose $\alpha < 0$, and $f(t)$ is decreasing, then we have from equation (3.2)

$$f'(t) = -\alpha \left((b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \right) \leq 0$$

Thus,

$$(b - t)^{\alpha-1} - t^{\alpha-1} \leq 0.$$

Hence,

$$t \geq \frac{b}{2}.$$

So, f is increasing on $[0, \frac{b}{2}]$ and decreasing on $[\frac{b}{2}, b)$. Hence, $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = f(0) = 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow b^-} f(t) = f(b) = 0$, i.e., $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = f(0)$ or $f(b)$. Thus, $\inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = 0$. Therefore, for any $0 \leq a < b$, $f(a) \geq \inf_{t \in [0, b)} f(t) = 0$, i.e.,

$$(b - a)^\alpha - b^\alpha + a^\alpha \geq 0,$$

that is,

$$b^\alpha - a^\alpha \leq (b - a)^\alpha.$$

□

4 Main results

Throughout this work, we make the following hypotheses:

h₁ there exists a constant $M > 0$ such that for any $y_1, y_2 \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$ we have

$$|G(y_1(x)) - G(y_2(x))| \leq M \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty \quad x \in Q$$

h₂ there exists a constant \hat{K} such that

$$\hat{K} = \sup_{x, t \in [0, 1]} \int_0^x |k(x, t)| dt < \infty$$

Theorem 3. (*Existence of Solution*). Assume that (h_1) and (h_2) holds, if

$$\left(\Lambda + \frac{\hat{K}M}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \right) < 1, \tag{4.1}$$

then there exists a solution $y \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$ to problem (1.1) – (1.2).

Proof. Let T be an operator such that $T : C(Q, \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow C(Q, \mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} (Ty)(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} x^k + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-\gamma_i-1} u_i(s)y(s)ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} g(s) ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) G(y(t)) dt \right) ds. \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

Our goal is to apply Schauder’s fixed point theorem. To do that, we will show that T satisfies the following;

- i T is Lipschitz,
- ii T sends bounded sets to bounded sets,
- iii T sends bounded sets to equicontinuous sets.

First, we note that T is well defined. Indeed, since $x \mapsto \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} x^k$, $x \mapsto \sum_{i=0}^n u_i(x) (I^{\alpha-\gamma_i} y)(x)$, $x \mapsto (I^\alpha g)(x)$, $x \mapsto \int_0^x k(x,t) G(y(t)) dt$ are continuous, the right hand of (4.2) is well defined and $x \mapsto (Ty)(x)$ is continuous. Thus, for $y \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$, $Ty \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$.

Let $a, b \in C(Q, \mathbb{R})$, for any $x \in [0, 1]$, we have by setting $E = |(Ta)(x) - (Tb)(x)|$

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \left| \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-\gamma_i-1} u_i(s) (a(s) - b(s)) ds \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) (G(a(t)) - G(b(t))) dt \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \left| \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-\gamma_i-1} u_i(s) (a(s) - b(s)) ds \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s k(s,t) (G(a(t)) - G(b(t))) dt \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-\gamma_i-1} |u_i(s)| |a(s) - b(s)| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s,t)| |G(a(t)) - G(b(t))| dt \right) ds \\ &\leq \sum_{i=0}^n \|u_i\|_\infty \|a - b\|_\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-\gamma_i-1} ds \\ &\quad + \hat{K}M \|a - b\|_\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-s)^{\alpha-1} ds. \end{aligned}$$

By property (iii) we have

$$|(Ta)(x) - (Tb)(x)| \leq \left(\Lambda + \frac{\hat{K}M}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \right) \|a - b\|_\infty, \text{ for all } x \in [0, 1]$$

Thus,

$$\|(Ta) - (Tb)\|_\infty \leq \Phi \|a - b\|_\infty,$$

where

$$\Phi = \Lambda + \frac{\hat{K}M}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

It follows that T is Lipschitz continuous.

Next, by *Lemma 2*, we can conclude that operator T (i.e T being Lipschitz) maps bounded sets to bounded sets in $C(Q, \mathbb{R})$.

Next, we show that T maps bounded sets to equicontinuous sets of $C(Q, \mathbb{R})$. Let $y \in B_\epsilon = \{y \in C(Q, \mathbb{R}) : \|y\|_\infty \leq \epsilon\}$, let $\sup_{x \in Q} |G(y(x))| \leq M \|y\|_\infty + G(0)$ and let $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 1]$ with $x_1 < x_2$. Setting $E = (Ty)(x_2) - (Ty)(x_1)$, then we have from (4.2)

$$\begin{aligned} |E| &= \left| \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k) \right. \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) ds \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) ds \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) ds \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) ds \right) \Big| \\ &\leq \left| \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) ds \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) ds \right) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) ds \right) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) ds \right) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |E| \leq & \left| \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k) \right| \\
 & + \left| \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) \right. \right. \\
 & - \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) \\
 & \left. \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y(s) \right) ds \right| \\
 & + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) - \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} g(s) \right) ds \right| \\
 & + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \right. \right. \\
 & - \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \\
 & \left. \left. + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y(t)) dt \right) \right) ds \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |E| \leq & \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k) \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds \right. \\
 & + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds \\
 & \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds \right. \\
 & + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds \left. \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \right. \\
 & + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \\
 & \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

The above inequality can be written as

$$|(Ty)(x_2) - (Ty)(x_1)| \leq A + B + C + D, \tag{4.3}$$

where

$$A = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k)$$

$$B = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds \right)$$

$$C = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds \right)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \right).$$

On Simplifying A by considering $(x_2^k - x_1^k) \leq (x_2 - x_1)$ for $0 \leq k \leq m - 1$, since $x_2, x_1 \in [0, 1]$ and $x_1 < x_2$ and taking $d_{k^*} = \max_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} \{d_k\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} (x_2^k - x_1^k) \\ &\leq \left(\frac{|d_1|}{1!} + \frac{|d_2|}{2!} + \dots + \frac{|d_{m-1}|}{(m-1)!} \right) (x_2 - x_1) \\ &= \frac{|d_{k^*}|}{k^*!} (m-1) (x_2 - x_1). \end{aligned}$$

On simplifying B and by property (iii) and Lemma 3 we have

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} |u_i(s)| |y(s)| ds \right) \\ &\leq \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\|u_i\|_\infty \|y\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i + 1)} \left((x_2 - x_1)^{\alpha - \gamma_i} + (x_2^{\alpha - \gamma_i} - (x_2 - x_1)^{\alpha - \gamma_i}) - x_1^{\alpha - \gamma_i} \right) \\ &= \Lambda \epsilon (x_2^{\alpha - \gamma_i} - x_1^{\alpha - \gamma_i}) \\ &\leq \Lambda \epsilon (x_2 - x_1)^{\alpha - \gamma_i}. \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying C , we use property (iii) and Lemma 3 as follows

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha - 1} |g(s)| ds \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \left((x_2 - x_1)^\alpha + (x_2^\alpha - (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha) - x_1^\alpha \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

To simplify D , we use property (iii) and *Lemma 3* as follows

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{x_1}^{x_2} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \right. \\ &\quad + \int_0^{x_1} (x_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^{x_1} (x_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s |k(s, t)| |G(y(t))| dt \right) ds \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\hat{K} (M \|y\|_\infty + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} ((x_2 - x_1)^\alpha + (x_2^\alpha - (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha - x_1^\alpha)) \\ &\leq \frac{K^* (M\epsilon + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, equation (4.3) is

$$\begin{aligned} |(Ty)(x_2) - (Ty)(x_1)| &\leq \frac{|d_{k^*}|}{k^*!} (m - 1) (x_2 - x_1) + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\|u_i\|_\infty \|y\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i + 1)} (x_2 - x_1)^{\alpha - \gamma_i} \\ &\quad + \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha + \frac{K^* (M\epsilon + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (x_2 - x_1)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

We see that the right hand side of the above equation is independent of y and tends to zero as $x_2 - x_1 \rightarrow 0$. This leads to $|(Ty)(x_2) - (Ty)(x_1)| \rightarrow 0$ as $x_2 \rightarrow x_1$ uniformly in y . Therefore, the set $\{Ty : y \in B_\epsilon\}$ is equicontinuous and finally, we need to show that there exists a closed convex bounded subset C of X such that $Tc \subseteq C$.

Consider $B_\epsilon = \{y \in C(Q, \mathbb{R}) : \|y\|_\infty \leq \epsilon\}$, we will show that for some $\epsilon > 0$, $TB_\epsilon \subseteq B_\epsilon$. For contradiction, suppose that $TB_\epsilon \not\subseteq B_\epsilon$ for all $\epsilon > 0$.

Let n be a positive integer, then there exists $y_n \in B_n$ such that $\|Ty_n\|_\infty > n$.

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} |(Ty_n)(x)| &\leq \left| \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{d_k}{k!} x^k \right| \left| \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} u_i(s) y_n(s) ds \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha-1} g(s) ds \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s k(s, t) G(y_n(t)) dt \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sup_{x \in [0,1]} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} x^k \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha - \gamma_i - 1} \sup_{s \in Q} |u_i(s)| \sup_{s \in Q} |y_n(s)| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha-1} \sup_{s \in Q} |g(s)| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - s)^{\alpha-1} \left(\int_0^s \sup_{s \in Q} |k(s, t)| \sup_{t \in Q} |G(y_n(t))| dt \right) ds \\ &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\|u_i\|_\infty \|y_n\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha - \gamma_i + 1)} \\ &\quad + \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} + \frac{\hat{K} (Mn + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}, \text{ for all } x \in [0, 1] \text{ text.} \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\|(Ty_n)\|_\infty \leq \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} + \Lambda n + \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{\hat{K}(Mn + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}.$$

Observe that if

$$\begin{aligned} n &< \|(Ty_n)\|_\infty \\ &< \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{k!} + \Lambda n + \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{\hat{K}(Mn + |G(0)|)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Dividing through by n we have,

$$1 < \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{|d_k|}{nk!} + \Lambda + \frac{\|g\|_\infty}{n\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{\hat{K}M}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}.$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain

$$1 < \Lambda + \frac{\hat{K}M}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}.$$

Which is a contradiction to equation (4.1). Hence, for some n_0 , $TB_{n_0} \subseteq B_{n_0}$.

Let $C := B_{n_0}$ and let $\hat{T} := T|_C$, i.e. $T : C \rightarrow C$ with $\hat{T}y = Ty$. By Arzelà-Ascoli thus, for any $(y_n)_n \subseteq C$, since C is bounded $(y_n)_n$ is bounded and by $(\hat{T}y_n)_n \equiv (Ty_n)_n$ is equicontinuous. Then there exists a subsequence $(\hat{T}y_{n_j})_j$ of $(\hat{T}y_n)_n$ which is convergent. Hence, \hat{T} is compact. By of Schauder's fixed point theorem, there exists a fixed point y of T in $C(Q, \mathbb{R})$. Then y is a solution of equation (1.1) – (1.2). \square

5 Numerical Illustration

Example 1 [42]. Consider the Volterra fractional integro-differential equation

$$D^{\frac{1}{2}}y(x) = \frac{8}{3\sqrt{\pi}}x^{\frac{3}{2}} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}}x^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{3}{12}x^5 + \frac{4}{12}x^4 + \int_0^x xty(t) dt. \quad (5.1)$$

Subject to $y(0) = 0$ with exact solution $y(x) = x^2 - x$.

Solution: Equation (5.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} |(Ty_2)(x) - (Ty_1)(x)| &= \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \int_0^x (x-s)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_0^s st(y_2(t) - y_1(t)) dt \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \int_0^x (x-s)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_0^s st|y_2(t) - y_1(t)| dt \right) ds \\ &\leq \frac{\|y_2 - y_1\|_\infty}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \int_0^x (x-s)^{-\frac{1}{2}} s^3 ds \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2 we have,

$$\|Ty_2 - Ty_1\|_\infty \leq \left(\frac{\Gamma(4) x^{3.5}}{\Gamma(4.5)} \right) \|y_2 - y_1\|_\infty$$

Thus,

$$\|Ty_2 - Ty_1\|_\infty \leq (0.51583) \|y_2 - y_1\|_\infty. \quad (5.2)$$

Since $0.51583 < 1$, we say that the problem satisfies the condition of Theorem 3.

Example 2. Consider the multi-term fractional order integro-differential equation

$$D^2y(x) - x^2D^{\frac{3}{2}}y(x) - \sqrt{x}D^{\frac{1}{2}}y(x) - \sqrt[3]{x}y(x) = 6\sqrt{\pi}x - 8\sqrt{x^7} - \frac{16}{5}x^3 - \sqrt[3]{x^{10}}\sqrt{\pi} + \int_0^x xt^2y(t) dt. \quad (5.3)$$

Subject to $y(0) = y'(0) = 0$ with exact solution $y(x) = \sqrt{\pi}x^3$.

Solution: Equation (5.3) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} |(Ty_2)(x) - (Ty_1)(x)| &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(2)\Gamma(1.5)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^{\frac{5}{2}}|y_2(s) - y_1(s)| ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(2)\Gamma(2.5)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^2|y_2(s) - y_1(s)| ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{\Gamma(2)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^{\frac{1}{3}}|y_2(s) - y_1(s)| ds \\ &+ \frac{1}{3\Gamma(2)} \int_0^x (x-s)|y_2(s) - y_1(s)| ds \\ &\leq \frac{\|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}}{\Gamma(2)\Gamma(1.5)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^{\frac{5}{2}} ds + \frac{\|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}}{\Gamma(2)\Gamma(2.5)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^2 ds \\ &+ \frac{\|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}}{\Gamma(2)} \int_0^x (x-s)s^{\frac{1}{3}} ds \\ &+ \frac{\|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}}{3\Gamma(2)} \int_0^x (x-s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2 we have

$$|(Ty_2)(x) - (Ty_1)(x)| \leq \left(\frac{\Gamma(3.5)x^{4.5}}{\Gamma(5.5)\Gamma(1.5)} + \frac{\Gamma(3)x^4}{\Gamma(2.5)\Gamma(5)} + \frac{\Gamma(\frac{4}{3})x^{\frac{7}{3}}}{\Gamma(\frac{10}{3})} + \frac{\Gamma(1)x^2}{3\Gamma(3)} \right) \|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}.$$

Thus,

$$\|Ty_2 - Ty_1\|_{\infty} \leq (0.62243) \|y_2 - y_1\|_{\infty}.$$

Since $0.62243 < 1$, we say that the problem satisfies the condition of the Theorem 3.

6 Conclusion

The problem of multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equation is successfully converted to its equivalent integral form using Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, a lemma is established to demonstrate the solution of the multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equation. We used Schauder's fixed point theorem in establishing the existence of the solution. Moreover, examples were considered to test the applicability of the proposed existence theorem for the solution of multi-term fractional order Volterra integro-differential equations.

References

- [1] Kilbas, A.A., Srivastava, H.M., and Trujillo, J. J. (2006). Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential Equations, Elsevier, Vol. 204.
- [2] Huang, L., and Bae, Y. (2018). Chaotic dynamics of the fractional-Love model with an external environment, Entropy **20**(1)53.

- [3] Zheng, L., and Zhang, X. (2017). Modeling and Analysis of Modern Fluid Problems, Academic Press, London, UK.
- [4] Mainardi, F. (2022). Fractional Calculus and Waves in Linear Viscoelasticity: An Introduction to Mathematical Models, World Scientific.
- [5] Baleanu, D., Jajarmi, A., and Hajipour, M. (2017). A new formulation of the fractional optimal control problems involving Mittag–Leffler nonsingular kernel, *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications* **175**(3), 718–737.
- [6] Erturk, V. S., Odibat, Z. M., and Momani, S. (2011). An approximate solution of a fractional order differential equation model of human T-cell lymphotropic virus I (HTLV-I) infection of CD4+ T-cells. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **62**(3) (2011), 996–1002.
- [7] Hilfer, R. (Ed.), (2000). Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics, World Scientific.
- [8] Magin, R. L. (2012). Fractional Calculus in Bioengineering: A Tool to Model Complex Dynamics, In Proceedings of the 13th International Carpathian Control Conference (ICCC), IEEE, pp. 464–469.
- [9] Fallahgoul, H., Focardi, S., and Fabozzi, F. (2016). Fractional Calculus and Fractional Processes with Applications to Financial Economics: Theory and Application, Academic Press.
- [10] Baleanu, D., and Lopes, A. M. (2019). Handbook of Fractional Calculus with Applications. Applications in Engineering, Life and Social Sciences, Part A, Southampton: Comput Mech Publicat, 7.
- [11] Tarasov, V. E. (2020). Mathematical Economics: Application of Fractional Calculus, *Mathematics* **8**(5) (2020), 660.
- [12] Bulut, H., Sulaiman, T. A., Baskonus, H. M., Rezazadeh, H., Eslami, M. and Mirzazadeh, M. (2018). Optical solitons and other solutions to the conformable space–time fractional Fokas–Lenells equation, *Optik* **172**, 20–27.
- [13] Zabadal, J., Vilhena, M., and Livotto, P. (2001). Simulation of chemical reactions using fractional derivatives, *Nuovo Cimento. B* **116**(5), 529–545.
- [14] Yang, F., and Zhu, K. Q. (2011). On the definition of fractional derivatives in rheology, *Theoretical and Applied Mechanics Letters* **1**(1), 012007.
- [15] Umar, D. and Bichi, S. L. (2024). Existence of solution of multi-term fractional order Fredholm integro-differential equation, *Bangmod J-MCS.*, Vol. 10 (2024) 30-47.
- [16] Umar, D. and Bichi, S. L. (2024). Uniqueness and convergence of solution of multi-term fractional order Fredholm Integro-differential equation, *FULafia journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 1-8
- [17] Umar, D. and Bichi, S. L. (2024). Uniqueness of solution of multi-term fractional order Volterra Integro-differential equations with convergence analysis. *International Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Modelling.* **7**(1), 12-22.
- [18] Balachandran, K., and Kiruthika, S. (2011). Existence results for fractional integrodifferential equations with nonlocal condition via resolvent operators, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **62**(3), 1350–1358.
- [19] Samko, S. G., Kilbas, A. A., and Marichev, O. I. (1993). Fractional Integrals and Derivatives, Vol. 1, Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, Yverdon-les-Bains, Switzerland.

- [20] Diethelm, K., and Ford, N. J. (2002). Analysis of fractional differential equations, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* **265**(2), 229–248.
- [21] Yuste, S. B., and Acedo, L. (2005). An explicit finite difference method and a new von Neumann-type stability analysis for fractional diffusion equations, *SIAM Journal on Numerical Analysis* **42**(5), 1862–1874.
- [22] Kilbas, A. A., and Marzan, S. A. (2005). Nonlinear differential equations with the Caputo fractional derivative in the space of continuously differentiable functions, *Differential Equations* **41**, 84–89.
- [23] Pilipovic, S. and Stojanovic, M. (2006). Fractional differential equations through Laguerre expansions in abstract spaces: Error estimates, *Integral Transforms and Special Functions* **17**(12), 877–887.
- [24] Agarwal, R. P., Benchohra, M., and Hamani, S. (2010). A survey on existence results for boundary value problems of nonlinear fractional differential equations and inclusions, *Acta Applicandae Mathematicae* **109**, 973–1033.
- [25] Baleanu, D., and Mustafa, O. G. (2010). On the global existence of solutions to a class of fractional differential equations, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **59**(5), 1835–1841.
- [26] Tian, Y., and Bai, Z. (2010). Existence results for the three-point impulsive boundary value problem involving fractional differential equations, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **59**(8), 2601–2609.
- [27] Wei, Z., Li, Q., and Che, J. (2010). Initial value problems for fractional differential equations involving Riemann–Liouville sequential fractional derivative, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* **367**(1), 260–272.
- [28] Anguraj, A., Karthikeyan, P., and Trujillo, J. J. (2011). Existence of solutions to fractional mixed integrodifferential equations with nonlocal initial condition, *Advances in Difference Equations* **2011**, 1–12.
- [29] Aghajani, A., Banaś, A., and Jalilian, Y. (2011). Existence of solutions for a class of nonlinear Volterra singular integral equations, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **62**(3), 1215–1227.
- [30] Idczak, D., and Kamocki, D. (2011). On the existence, uniqueness, and formula for the solution of RL fractional Cauchy problem in R^n , *Fractional Calculus and Applied Analysis* **14**, 538–553.
- [31] Kostic, A. (2011). Abstract time-fractional equations: existence and growth of solutions, *Fractional Calculus and Applied Analysis* **14**(2), 301–316.
- [32] Agarwal, R. P., and Ahmad, B. (2011). Existence theory for anti-periodic boundary value problems of fractional differential equations and inclusions, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **62**(3), 1200–1214.
- [33] Hu, Z., and Liu, W. (2011). Solvability for fractional order boundary value problems at resonance, *Boundary Value Problems* **2011**(1), 1–10.
- [34] Aghajani, A., Jalilian, Y., and Trujillo, J. J. (2012). On the existence of solutions of fractional integro-differential equations, *Fractional Calculus and Applied Analysis* **15**(2012), 44–69.
- [35] Hamoud, A., Ghadle, K., and Atshan, S. (2019). The approximate solutions of fractional integro-differential equations by using modified Adomian decomposition method, *Khayyam Journal of Mathematics* **5**(1) (2019), 21–39.

-
- [36] Rui, W. (2011). Existence of solutions of nonlinear fractional differential equations at resonance, *Electronic Journal of Qualitative Theory of Differential Equations* **2011**(66), 1–12.
- [37] Caballero, J., Harjani, J., and Sadarangani, K. (2011). On existence and uniqueness of positive solutions to a class of fractional boundary value problems, *Boundary Value Problems* **2011**(1), 1–9.
- [38] Wazwaz, A. M. (2011). *Linear and Nonlinear Integral Equations*, Springer, Berlin.
- [39] Deimling, K. (1985). *Nonlinear Functional Analysis*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, New York.
- [40] Zeidler, E. (1986). *Nonlinear Functional Analysis and its Applications, Part 1: Fixed-Point Theorems*, Springer.
- [41] Berinde, V. (2007). *Iterative Approximation of Fixed Points*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [42] Kumar, K., Pandey, R. K. and Sharma, S. Comparative study of three numerical schemes for fractional integro-differential equations, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* **315** (2017), 287–302.